

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Guerra****FIRST NAME: Heitor****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert some references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MSWord 2010

OUTCOME OF THE ACADEMIC WRITING REVIEW

1) INTRODUCTION

As mentioned by Prof. Izet Masic, for a person devote itself to science and research, it is necessary to possess the following qualities: intelligence, skills of analysis and synthesis, the power of observation, perseverance, creativity, ethics and responsibility. In addition, the scientific and research circles, the citation is the information that is necessary to the reader in identifying and finding used sources by the author during the preparation in specific paper. Thus, a solid understanding of characteristic of citations is required before preparation of a research or scientific paper.

As an example, I have been exposed to environmental and social works over the last 12 years in which, I was been required to prepare reports to various stakeholders relying on others written property. The preparation of social and environmental reports required acknowledgement of other writers' words in previous works or studies, therefore, I found the content of the first course of my doctorate program with Euclid University very helpful and surely, will contribute for the presentation of my doctorate papers and work-related reports. Moreover, no matter what the area is related with the work being prepared, writing skills are always very useful, specially for me, as I am not native English speaker.

In this paper, I will focus on citation, its importance and how to do, based on various sources of information in use for preparation of any specific paper.

2) CITATION

a) What is Citation?

Citation is the method used to indicate where a piece of information came from, and serves to give to the readers the information necessary to find another source, from where the certain material in the work were extracted from, and may include information about the author, title of the work, name and location of the publisher, date and page number of the material we are borrowing.

Citing sources helps our readers to distinguish our ideas from those of other sources and will emphasize the originality of our work.

Sometimes, access to the original work is not possible, so we are required to quote indirectly from a text in which we did not have access to the original, based on a quote from another author. The problem with this type of citation can be raised when the source of the work in use does not correspond to the original text in whole or partly, creating problems of interpretation and argumentation (Gabaldi, 2009). In these cases, we are required to include the identification of author cited and the date of the original work, followed by the space and the Latin word "*apud*," and then by the name of the author / from whose the quote was extracted, including the date and page. Example: Kabiru, 2019 *apud* Heitor, 2020:14.

On other hand, changing the words of an original source is not sufficient to prevent plagiarism (Hunter, 2017, Student Affairs Repository). Accordingly, if someone has retained the essential idea of an original of an original source, and have not cited it, then no matter how drastically has altered its context or presentation, still considered plagiarized.

b) Importance of Citing

The main reason of citing is to avoid plagiarism. Other benefits of citing are:

Give more insight to the reader about our ideas and from where they came from; It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit (EUCLID 2015, 12);

Give an idea to the reader about the amount of research done during the preparation of the work; and

Strengtheness of our work by lending other one's ideas.

Whenever we borrow words or ideas, we need acknowledge their source. The following situations always require citing:

- Whenever we use quotes;
- Whenever we paraphrase;

- Whenever we use an idea that someone else has already expressed; and
- Whenever we make specific reference to the work of another.

EUCLID (2015) mentioned that there are two things about two things about citing we will need to be aware of, namely in text citations and list of works cited (15).

c) How Cite

EUCLID (2015) provides guidance on how to cite while preparing a paper; although, the author mentioned that, ‘In a paper it does not look very good if you have too many quotes (16-28). Therefore, we will need to paraphrase at time, that is, write other one’s ideas in our own words.

EUCLID’s ACA-401D in 2015, mentions the following method of citation:

In-text citation: that refers to citing the piece of working we are using within our actual text and the more commonly used as quotations and paraphrases, and

List of work cited: is the bibliography or reference listed at the end of the book and provides publication information for each of the sources cited in the paper (EUCLID 2015, 33).

In addition, is important to consider that when writing essays, papers, dissertation or theses, it is essential that approved referencing conventions are followed and that particular attention is paid to capitalisation, the use of italics and punctuation. Lectures, tutors and external examiners usually insist on correctly formulated citations and references.

3) CONCLUSION

I found interesting the introductory course ACA-401D as it will help on the preparation of my paper throughout the doctorate program.

I look forward applying the writing concepts of writing acquired during this course, and the guidance should assist me in understanding how to deal with academic sources without resorting to plagiarism.

As mentioned, I am not native English speaker and the American and British basic differences and influences of change provided me a deeper diving on basic spelling concepts, as most of time the differences are not easily understood for us (EUCLID 2015, 54-59).

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